

Recollections from Colleagues in the Department of Chemical Engineering at Imperial College London

Nilay Shah*. Clemens Brechtelsbauer*
Benoît Chachuat*. Daryl Williams*.
Claire Adjiman*. Senait Selassie*

**Department of Chemical Engineering, Imperial College London,
UK, (e-mail: n.shah@imperial.ac.uk, c.brechtelsbauer@imperial.ac.uk,
c.adjiman@imperial.ac.uk, c.adjiman@imperial.ac.uk, s.selassie@imperial.ac.uk).*

Abstract: Nina joined the Department of Chemical Engineering at Imperial College London in 2007, as the ABB/Royal Academy of Engineering Chair. She continued being an active member of the Centre for Process Systems Engineering, but also took on leadership roles in the Department, interacting with colleagues across the Department.

Keywords: Kindness, generosity, true leader, calmness, mentor.

1. NILAY SHAH

Professor of Process Systems Engineering, Head of
Department

I have known Nina Thornhill for over 20 years; we first interacted through the Centre for Process Systems Engineering (while she was at UCL) where we had some joint interests in data analysis and fault detection. I remember as a young academic working on a related project with BP and visiting her at UCL where she was extremely helpful and went out of her way to provide a lot of very useful guidance on how to analyse operational data. Of course this is the field in which she has developed an outstanding international reputation and it certainly helped us deliver a good project.

In those early days I very much enjoyed her presentations at the CPSE Industrial Consortium meeting; they were invariably very clear and well-structured and found the right balance between conveying the leading edge innovations and the practical application (a skill that was not always evident in all the talks!). We had some interesting conversations at the time about how graph theory could be used to complement time series analysis and this again proved to be an area that Nina developed some very novel technology in.

When I was part of the Executive Team and Director of Undergraduate Studies in Imperial's Department of Chemical Engineering, Nina expressed interest in moving to Imperial and taking up an ABB Chair (around 2007). At that time, our department had a culture of recruiting early career staff and was not used to "experienced hires"; this strategy had served us well so it was our default approach. We were therefore somewhat cautious about the concept but knew Nina well. She gave an amazing account of herself and it was a no-brainer to go for it. She also brought an excellent relationship with ABB who have become one of the Department's strongest

industrial partners. Our "experiment" of this senior hire was so successful that we completely changed our policy after recruiting Nina and have since then explicitly sought new candidates at all career stages.

Nina is a true leader in that she leads by example and by demonstrating that leadership in academia is provision of a service to the community and not the pursuit of glory. Once she had settled in to the Department she took on what I believe to be the hardest role of Director of Undergraduate Studies. In our Department, this person has the responsibility for ensuring a well-run, ambitious and internationally leading undergraduate programme for 400-500 demanding students. It's a role Nina took on with relish and she brought an ambitious, super-organised and meticulous style to the job. This also comes with being a member of the Department's senior management team ("the Executive Committee") where we overlapped for some time. Her contributions to the running of the Department and the educational programme in these roles were exceptional and she set some peer expectations around professionalism and organisation that I certainly needed to sort myself out to meet! I know that my colleague Klaus Hellgardt who took over from Nina was very grateful for how easy she made the handover and the state of the administration he was able to inherit.

An interesting thing about working with Nina is she always seems to anticipate issues and act on them before they actually need to be dealt with. It's quite often that I'll get a message from Nina and she's sorted out something that I was going to get around to discussing with her. This proactive and collaborative approach makes it a joy to have Nina as a colleague. She's everything you would want in a successful academic: creative, clever, kind, an amazing mentor (as all the stories in this volume will attest), thoughtful, professional and selfless. I hope she looks back on all she has done with a

sense of achievement and satisfaction, because that is the least that she should feel.

2. CLEMENS BRECHTELSBAUER

Director of Chemical Engineering Education.

When I heard in 2013 that Nina would take over as my manager for the next couple of years, I was at first a bit apprehensive. I enjoyed an excellent working relationship with my boss at the time and she was pretty much an unknown quantity to me. Nevertheless, he tried to reassure me: "Don't worry. She is a programmer, she thinks like you. You'll like her." I thought that was a bit odd, as I had last programmed something more than 20 years ago, in Fortran to boot, so I wasn't exactly up to scratch in modern programming. However, his judgment proved to be right on the money. Nina and I hit it off from the beginning. She is very organized and process driven, like me, which made working with her go like a charm. In fact, she remarked on this in one of my first appraisals.

I learned a lot from her, particularly in the context of leading a professional accreditation of a study programme, which would come in useful years later. As a colleague she was very kind and supportive with just the right amount of steel under the surface so you knew you who's boss and you could count on her when the going got tough. I couldn't have wished for a better manager. And the fact that she frequently brought biscuits to our leadership team meetings didn't hurt either.

3. BENOÎT CHACHUAT

Reader in Process Systems Engineering, CPSE Associate Director

It has been a great pleasure getting to work with Nina over the past decade. Her collaboration with ABB in the area of process monitoring and fault diagnosis has been one of the pillars of the CPSE industrial consortium. I was delighted when she was recognised with the Nordic Process Control Award for her outstanding work in this area. As a teacher, Nina's control course was always of the highest standards. She has trained many cohorts of chemical engineers and produced impressive course material that is still in use today.

Nina was also a great mentor to me when I was took over the control coursework project and she was very supportive when I revamped that project to introduce Simulink a few years later---then in her capacity as Director of Undergraduate Studies. I shall be ever so grateful to Nina for her wonderful contributions, her great support, her kindness, and for being so respectful to others. I wish her all the very best in her retirement!

4. DARYL WILLIAMS

Professor of Particle Science, Director of Discovery Space

Nina distinguished herself by working closely with industrial partners on problems that were industrially relevant as well as being both scientifically demanding and academically rigorous - her long-term support by both the Royal Academy of Engineering and ABB are testament to her highly successful approach to engineering research.

5. CLAIRE ADJIMAN

Professor of Chemical Engineering, CPSE Director

I have known Nina since joining CPSE about 20 years ago and I have been struck by her measured approach to all situations, her positive outlook and her strong interest in others. She is always prepared to listen and encourage, be it with colleagues, students or collaborators. Nina takes a reflective and well-thought out approach to all she does, putting the same dedication and from small engagements such as research presentations and PhD viva, to much larger projects such as helping to deliver a new carbon dioxide capture pilot plant for the department.

While she is always calm, it is also evident she takes tremendous joy in her work, in her collaborations and in celebrating the success of others. She practices an unusual and highly successful mix of academic research embedded in practice and sets an example for all on how to develop outstanding partnerships. It is an absolute pleasure to interact with Nina and to learn a bit more each time about her unique approach to research.

6. SENAIT SELASSIE

CPSE External Relations Manager

I have known Nina Thornhill for over 15 years at the Centre for Process Systems (CPSE). When I first met Nina she was a member of CPSE and working at UCL. We were all thrilled when she moved to Imperial College. Nina is awesome and inspires everyone around her.

Nina is the Academic 'Friend' for ABB and she has been the link to the CPSE Industrial Consortium for many years. When Nina presents at industrial meetings, she has an amazing skill in pitching it at the right level so the audience are engaged and able to follow her talk (as Nilay Shah mentioned, this is not always evident in all the talks).

What I will always remember Nina for is her kindness and generosity. For example, despite being busy, Nina will send me her presentation in PowerPoint to make it easy for me to upload on the computer before the event and she will also send a PDF copy so I do not have to convert it and can upload it on the website. No one else does this and is an example of one of the many ways Nina has made my time at CPSE a joy. Nina epitomises academia and I feel fortunate to have learned so much from her.